

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE ARTISANAL MINING OF TIN AND COLUMBITE ON ABANDONED MINES OF BISICHI JENTA LTD, KURU (NARAGUTA SHEET 168) PLATEAU STATE, NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA

Stephen J. Mallo and Caleb Aluwong
Department of Geology and Mining, University of Jos, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The discovery of tin on the Jos Plateau in the early 1900s heralded the influx of several foreign and indigenous mining companies. Mention must be made especially of events in the 1950s when the introduction of mechanized mining by such mining companies like the Bisichi Jenta Ltd resulted in higher production of minerals. Bisichi Jenta Ltd a British mining company held several mining leases on the Jos Plateau and the neighboring states of the present Adamawa and Nasarawa States. An investigation into the mining activities of this company suggests that the company stood out amongst its peers especially with regards to the effective deployment of hydraulic mining equipments and specifically the hydraulic Jigs which were later to be redesigned with the ingenuity of a Nigerian Engineer to meet local needs and consequently earning the patented name of Jentar Jigs internationally. The mining of cassiterite along old streams in the Kuru area witnessed the exploitation of tin and Columbite initially in alluvial deposits at the downstream areas and graduating into alluvial deposits midstream and subsequently upstream to the primary source consisting of decomposed granite. The hydraulic mining operation in the 1920s concentrated in the mining of tin and Columbite deposits with cut-off grades of more than 0.6g/ton. The present artisanal mining however, is being carried out on abandoned low grades of 0.1g/ton. The low grade notwithstanding, at the present economic value (local market price) of N4, 500.00/Kg (\$27.00/Kg) still provides a formidable source of income to the artisanal miners. The mining activity which involves the random sinking of mining pits for the exploitation of the mineral, with devastating effect on the environment as opened pits are not reclaimed after mining. The study has revealed the existence of Six (6) Mining Clusters providing employment to over 2500 artisanal miners. The miners are involved in sub-surface mining of tin and Columbite at one of such Clusters (the Main Mining Cluster) alone record daily earnings of between N100,000.00 to N150, 000.00 accruing to each active mine pit of about ten(10) team members of local miners. The total earnings per day for the twenty five (25) studied active pits on the average stand at about N3, 125,000.00 million (about \$18,600 dollars). The individual average daily earnings of about N 12,500(\$74.00 dollars) makes economic sense for these miners especially when viewed happening in a national economy with a per capita earning of less than \$1 dollar (N168.00) per day.

KEYWORDS: Artisanal Mining; Sub-surface Mining; Primary Deposits; Paddock; Alluvial Deposits; Ground Sluice Box

INTRODUCTION

Kuru is a district in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State North Central Nigeria, located on Naraguta SE, Sheet 168. The study area falls within the following coordinates latitude $9^{\circ}40'46.56''N$ – $9^{\circ}42'35.32''N$ and longitude $E8^{\circ}50'26.06''$ – $E8^{\circ}53'43.26''E$ (Fig 1)

The study area (Kuru) is made up of settlements like; Science School Kuru, Kuru Karama and Kuru Babba. Kuru is an old mining town boarded by some other mining villages such as Bisichi in the Northeast and Bukuru- Rayfield to the north. It is essentially known for the mining of tin and columbite with other associate minerals such as tantalum and kaolin.

The brief history of mining of cassiterite and columbite in the Study area as narrated by Engr. D. T. Pwajok a veteran mining Engineer of the Bisichi Jentar Ltd and erstwhile General Manager of the defunct Nigerian Mining Corporation shows that mining started in the area in 1920. Due to fluctuation of price of minerals in the global market, stock market; International Tin and Columbite Control (ITCC) was established to counter the fall in price whenever there was a fall in demand which is synonymous to OPEC. The sub-surface mining (Lotto) according to Pwajok, started way back from 1955, as at then, the minerals were mined at two pounds per-cubic feet (cut-off grade) and anything less than that was considered unprofitable. Presently the artisanal miners mine grades of ore as low as 0.2 pounds per cubic feet. Mining activities were carried out by three (3) major companies on the Plateau namely; the Amalgamated Tin Mining Company of Nigeria (ATMN) and Bisichi-Jentar (established by Jentu and Tarbot from U.K who owned the company then). The surface mining activities in the study area took place on deposits made up of primary (decomposed granite- found in place within the parent rock) and alluvial deposits (found along streams and old river channels). Other places with primary mineralization of cassiterite and columbite include Udegi – Nassarawa State, Rayfield – Jos South Local Government.

Within the study area there are lots of mine dumps the reason being that up to 1946, there was no restoration clause in the law so miners dumped their waste without restoring the mines which has contributed to many unclaimed mined ponds on the Jos Plateau today. In 1946 the laws were amended stating that 80% of the mines must be restored after any mining before new mining licenses can be re-issued.

The Jig was used for the mining of both tin and columbite, using their difference in specific gravity. The processes are; 1. First blast the rock; 2. Use the gravity pump to wash the minerals at the paddock working face and finally to the jig where the minerals are sorted (Mallo, 2000).

Fig.1. Satellite image showing mining clusters within Kuru and environs

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of research involved on the spot assessment and field measurements of the study area using various tools which include Global Positioning System (GPS), Compass, Tape, Camera, Field notebook and writing materials. The use of Google-Earth was employed in order to extract the map of the study area. The locations of the Mining Clusters were obtained from alluvial and primary deposits with the aid of GPS which was used to pick up the coordinates and then inserted on a Georeferenced map, using the software ILWIS 3.1 Academic. The digitized map was exported out of ILWIS 3.1 Academic into Microsoft word for further editing.

Field work: The field work involved the study of six (6) Mining Clusters mainly, The Main Cluster, Eastern Cluster, Western Cluster, South-Western Cluster 1, The South Western Cluster 2 and The Southern Cluster respectively all covering a total land area of 1.34km² (Table.1).

Table 1. Locations of Mining Clusters

S/No.	Clusters	GPS Coordinates	Area of Devastation
1	Main Cluster	9°41'46.91"N 8°53'00.55"E	0.334 km ²
2	Eastern Cluster	9°41'49.37"N 8°53'11.62"E	0.075 km ²
3	Western (Primary Deposit)Cluster	9°41'43.69"N 8°51'30.40"E	0.600 km ²
4.	Southern Cluster	9°41'26.37"N 8°53'18.76"E	0.194 km ²
5	South-western cluster 1	9°41'13.93"N 8°53'18.76"E	0.064 km ²
6	South-western cluster 2	9°41'31.11"N 8°51'20.03"E	0.074 km ²

Location 1: The Main Mining Cluster (Gada Biyu)(N09°41'50.1"; E 08° 52'01.4"and Elevation: 1236m). Artisanal mining started in Gada Biyu 2006, it was located on the opposite side of the present Gada Biyu (across the road), the mine site was later abandoned because cut-off grade of the ore was not favourable then, the miners therefore relocated to Gero, Bisichi and Barkin Ladi mining areas of Plateau State.

Location 2: Primary Columbite Paddock (PCP) (Latitude N 09°41'30.2" Longitude E08°51'20.0" & Elevation: 1260m). This large mine site is being reworked in search of Tin and Columbite. The deposit is from a primary source (decomposed granite) which was mined around 1950s' and left un-reclaimed. The mine site cannot be restored to more than 2% as no amount of dump can be used to fill the largely excavated area. Abandoned mining pits litter the area. Despite its devastated nature and threat to human lives and livestock, farmers were seen using the ponds for irrigation purposes (vegetable like pepper, tomato and beans) were being plant on the higher plains. Reworking of the old mine and opening up of new mine-faces from the existing one was seen currently going on by artisanal miners (Figs 5 &6).

Locations 3; 4; 5; &6. These comprise of the Eastern; Southern, South-Western 1; and the South-Western2 Clusters. The Eastern and Southern Clusters are located in alluvial deposits while the South-Western 1 and 2 Clusters are located on decomposed granite deposits. At these locations several active and non-active mining pits were sighted with several artisanal miners on duty.

Geology

Kuru is generally characterized by the abundant occurrence of the Younger Granite rocks which were emplaced during the Jurassic era. The formation of the Younger Granite is associated with the hot spot magmatism. The rock bodies are massif occurring ring complexes. The Younger Granites are known for hosting tin and columbite within Jos Bukuru and environs (Mallo, 2011).

Mine Development/ Extraction

Mine Development is accomplished through a series of vertical pits (shafts) (Fig 2, 3 &4) while the extraction of mineral is done using diggers and shovels. In the study area and specifically on the Main Cluster, twenty five (25) active mining pits and twelve (12) active sluice boxes were sighted (Tables 2&3). The non-active mine pits which by far outnumber the active ones, were found to be 67 in numbers. The tables provide the exact locations and elevations of active mine pits and ground sluice boxes which can serve as reference data for future geo-technical study of the sub-surface soil/rock structures. The development and extraction of minerals is accomplished through the mine syndicate system consisting of about ten team members. The mine syndicate is further divided into two, such that while about three (3) people are developing new shafts, seven (7) members would be involved in extraction and processing. Women are primarily involved in the haulage of ore to the ground sluice boxes. The major mining functions are as follows:

- Digging – digging extends to depth of between 30ft – 50ft, the shallowest pits being about 30ft with a diameter of 2.5 – 3ft., tools used include digger, shovel, torch light and wheel and bucket. When the wash (ore) is hit, the thickness is determined and the mining is accomplished along the strike.
- Extraction-Excavation of horizontal openings is carried out along the trend of mineralization. Horizontal opening can extent to about 60ft, depending on the extent of mineralization or availability of oxygen within the sub-surface.
- De-watering – A water pump machine is used to extract water out of the mine pit into neighbouring pit otherwise known as the ‘cotonia’. Two types of water pumps are used which are; the 2-inch inlet and outlet pump and 3-inch water inlet and outlet pump. The 2-inch water pump is considered to be more efficient because of its higher water pumping height.
- Haulages – the use of wheel and bucket to extract the wash from the well to the surface is employed by the miners while women further haul the mineral ore in head pans to the ground sluice boxes locations..
- Processing – They use rudimentary method in the absence of mechanized method. Ground sluicing boxes are designed in a manner that the wash passes through several stages pushed by flowing water delivered by water pumps. The lighter materials float pass while the denser materials (those with higher specific gravity) tin, columbite and iron trailing behind.
- Mine illumination/Ventilation-Candles and torchlight are used for illumination within the shaft, though torches are more preferable because it reduces competition of air consumption between the individual and candles as well as reduces heat generation within the hole. There was no evidence of any mine ventilation with miners sweating profusely.

Fig2. Contour Map of Kuru showing the locations Mining Clusters

Fig.3.An over-view of the Main Mine Site

Table2. Elevations and Location of active wells

S/No	Elevation (m)	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)
1	1249	09 ⁰ 41'48.9"	08 ⁰ 52'52.7"
2	1242	09 ⁰ 41'49."	08 ⁰ 52'56.9"
3	1242	09 ⁰ 41'48.5"	08 ⁰ 52'56.1"
4	1241	09 ⁰ 41.48"	08 ⁰ 52'55.6"
5	1240	09 ⁰ 41'48"	08 ⁰ 52'55.2"
6 Cluster of 5 wells	1241	09 ⁰ 41'28.1"	08 ⁰ 52'55.9"
7	1242	09 ⁰ 41'47.7"	08 ⁰ 52'52.2"
8	1241	09 ⁰ 41'48.3"	08 ⁰ 52'54"
9	1242	09 ⁰ 41'48.3"	08 ⁰ 52'54.5"
10	1239	09 ⁰ 41'48.5"	08 ⁰ 52'54.4"
11	1242	09 ⁰ 41'48.6"	08 ⁰ 52'54.1"
12	1238	09 ⁰ 41'49.2"	08 ⁰ 52'53.7"
13	1239	09 ⁰ 41'49.1"	08 ⁰ 52'51.6"
14	1239	09 ⁰ 41'49.1"	08 ⁰ 52'51.6"
15	1239	09 ⁰ 41'49.7"	08 ⁰ 52'50.5"
16	1242	09 ⁰ 41'49.5"	08 ⁰ 52'50.3"
17	1237	09 ⁰ 41'49.2"	08 ⁰ 52'50"
18	1243	09 ⁰ 41'52.5"	08 ⁰ 52'47.4"
19	1243	09 ⁰ 41'52.5"	08 ⁰ 52'47.4"
20	1245	09 ⁰ 41'46.7"	08 ⁰ 52'03.8"
21	1238	09 ⁰ 41'46.4"	08 ⁰ 52'03.8"

Table3. Elevations and Locations of Ground Sluice Boxes

S/No.	Elevation (m)	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)
1	1234	09 ⁰ 41'48.5"	08 ⁰ 52'57.8"
2	1249	09 ⁰ 41'48.9"	08 ⁰ 52'57.2"
3	1236	09 ⁰ 41'50.2"	08 ⁰ 52'57"
4	1244	09 ⁰ 41'48.5"	08 ⁰ 52'54"
5	1245	09 ⁰ 41'49.7"	08 ⁰ 52'53.7"
6	1240	09 ⁰ 41'49.3"	08 ⁰ 52'53"
7 Cluster of 5 boxes	1238	09 ⁰ 41'48.6"	08 ⁰ 52'53.01"
8	1243	09 ⁰ 41'52.8"	08 ⁰ 52'48.1"

Fig.4 Rudimentary Haulage and tin Processing Technique

Fig.5. Abandoned mine pit at the Primary Paddock

Fig.6. An overview of the Primary Paddock

Marketing

In a lotto where there is a sufficient quantity of ore, one pit can produce one wheel yield of 19kg of tin, columbite and other accessory minerals. One (1) bucket wheel of hauled ore represents one (1) bucket wheel yield consisting of 19kg of tin with specific gravity 5 and 28.8kg of Columbite with a usual specific gravity 7. Accessory minerals associated with the tin ore include zircon, iron and monazite with less than 1% total. Presently, a bucket wheel will yield at least 3cups of the tin concentrate after processing. On the average in a day, the artisanal miners can deliver to the surface about 15 bucket wheels, which translates to 45cups of tin daily.

On extraction of the material, it is buretted, the purity (grade) is scaled at 18.0. This is the highest grade and is sold at about N4200 per kg. If the burette value falls between 18.6 and 19.2, then it is sold between N3500 – N4000 per kg, any burette value greater than 19.2 is considered to be low grade.

In 2006, the market situation was more favourable as one (1) bucket wheel yielded one (1) bag of Columbite, with tin and iron then considered as accessory minerals. At present however given the same production rate (15 bucket wheel per/day) and at the cost of 1cup standing at N1000 – N2300 depending on the grade of the wash the daily revenue accrual per production pit (N2000 x 45 cups) is N90,000. The tin concentrates is sold to meddle men who in turn either resale or process same for export. The tin processing Sheds include: Kingsley – At Anguldi Jos; Spectrum – At Industrial estate Old airport road (Main Exported); Gidan Kumar – At Dadin Kowa Jos (Main export), Gidan Emma – At Dadin Kowa Jos; Chike Mills – Bukuru (Exporter), Gidan Ayara – Anguldi, and Gidan D. B. Zang. The dressed minerals are not smelted but exported raw.

DISCUSSION

The mining activity is of great economic and social significance. As it currently exists, artisanal mining in Kuru is high risk activity. The activity is practiced on a small scale by people who are often poor, and although educated, they lack other employment opportunities. It is a highly unregulated sector and subject to harsh working conditions. That the artisanal miners are not trained, they often do not realize that the un-supported and / or un-reclaimed pits of sub-surface mining methods they use to mine minerals are devastating their environment and their health with potential fatal consequences. This un-scientific method of mining lives behind devastated land area with abandoned pits and mine dumps littering the environment. This artisanal mining activity although constitutes a menace to the environment as the mined out pits are not reclaimed through adequate re-filling to forestall roof collapse leading to land subsidence, provide a formidable source of income to the miners. The surface mining of the primary tin deposit has also stripped hundreds of square kilometers of topsoil further reducing the arable land within the locality.

CONCLUSION

Although generating millions of Naira in earnings for the miners and supporting a large population of miners in the locality, artisanal mining has a devastating effect on the existing streams and the arable land of the people. The rudimentary sub-surface methods of mining being deployed which is un-supported, un-illuminated and un-ventilated portends serious dangers to the miners in terms of accidental roof collapses, suffocation and other forms of health hazards. This calls for some urgent need for regulation and effective monitoring by the appropriate Agencies of the Federal Government in line with best practices.

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Corresponding author

Stephen J. Mallo

Department of Geology and Mining, University of Jos, Nigeria